

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

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**БИОМОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ ВИДОВ
МОРСКИХ КАПУСТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ИХ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ**

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются биоморфологические особенности морской капусты различных видов. Показаны возможности применения морской капусты в различных отраслях. Большое место в работе занимает рассмотрение видов по особенностям их использования. В статье так же дается характеристика этим видам. Исследование ведется через рассмотрение таких проблем, как йододефицит и улучшение иммунитета, которая наиболее актуальна в наше время.

Ключевые слова: морская капуста, биоморфология, местообитания, использование

**BIOMORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF VARIOUS TYPES OF SEA
CABBAGE AND PROSPECTS FOR THEIR USE**

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Annotation: The article discusses the biomorphological features of seaweed of various species. The possibilities of using seaweed in various industries are shown. A large place in the work is occupied by the consideration of species according to the peculiarities of their use. The article also gives a description of these species. The research is conducted through consideration of such problems as

iodine deficiency and improvement of immunity, which is most relevant in our time.

Keywords: seaweed, biomorphology, habitats, usage

The relevance of today is the correction of the nutrition of the Republic of Kazakhstan, where negative trends in the health of the population are aggravated by the consequences of an unfavorable environmental situation. The basic principles of solving this problem are formulated in the Concept of the state policy in the field of healthy nutrition of our country. Iodine, the content of which is high in seaweed removes toxins and heavy metals from the human body. For the younger generation, whose body is just being formed, this is certainly important [1].

Diseases associated with iodine deficiency are common non-communicable diseases. For the prevention of iodine deficiency diseases, iodine-rich foods are introduced into food. One of the main sources of natural iodine is kelp. It has been established that the use of these algae improves the vitamin and mineral composition of the product. Kelp is included in the formulations of various food products [2-3].

Sea cabbage, a useful, edible algae. It belongs to the class of brown algae, which are distinguished by a rich set of useful trace elements and nutrients. Algae is filtered out of seawater, and then processed into a form acceptable to the human body [4].

What is included in the composition of seaweed?

1. A complete set of macro- and microelements such as phosphorus, sodium, iron, magnesium, iodine.
2. All vitamins from group B, as well as in large quantities E, A, C and D. Moreover, there are several times more vitamins and trace elements in seaweed than in ordinary [4].
3. Natural enterosorbents called "Alginates". They are designed to rid the body of toxins, ions, radionuclides and pathogenic bacteria.
4. Sterols, which prevent the accumulation of excess cholesterol and dilute the blood, thereby reducing vascular thrombosis.
5. An organically bound form of iodine that maintains the balance of this element in the body.
6. Dietary fiber, they are also pectins, which help to improve the functioning of the digestive system and gastrointestinal tract.
7. Fatty acids that prevent the appearance of atherosclerosis in old age.
8. Proteins and the most useful amino acids for the body.

9. High-molecular-weight polysaccharides that normalize metabolism, monitor cholesterol levels, water and salt balance, and prevent blood clots from forming [4].

Sea cabbage or *Laminaria*, in Japanese – "kombu" and in Chinese – "tsei", grows in huge thickets in the Arctic Ocean, Atlantic and Pacific Oceans, as well as in the seas: Okhotsk, Bering and White and in the Tatar Strait. In the northern parts of the sea, with colder water, sea cabbage reaches gigantic sizes and occupies huge areas of the bottom in large thickets. In the southern parts of the sea, Sea cabbage is smaller, thinner and pale brown with a noticeable redness. Japanese seaweed – *Laminaria japonica* Aresch., which in the fishing areas of the Tatar Strait, such as in the bays of Olga, Transfiguration, etc., prevails over other species, is mainly used for food. Sea cabbage has the appearance of a long, more or less thick, narrow or wide, flat leafy layer on a short or long petiole, at the bottom of which there is a bundle of branched attachment organs (rhizoids). In the northern parts of the Japanese, etc. sea cabbage reaches 3.5-5 meters or more in length and from 9-37 cm in width. In the northern seas, seaweed of other species reaches gigantic sizes and various widths, for example, *Laminaria digitata* reaches 1.5 meters wide or more, grows at various depths from 1-27 meters [5].

Next, we will consider and analyze the most promising and common types of sea cabbage. There are many types of sea cabbage in the world that can be useful in one way or another, but we have selected only 3 main types for analysis: *Saccharina latissima*, *Laminaria digitata* and *Laminaria angustata*.

1. *Saccharina latissima* is a species of brown algae from the genus *Saccharina*. Under the name "sea cabbage" is used for food. It is cultivated in a number of countries [6].

Biomorphological features. Kelp thallus is parenchymal (tissue), the level of its differentiation is one of the highest among algae: The shape of the thallus is ribbon-shaped, smooth or mesh-wrinkled, the width of the plate is from 1 to 13 m in length, in the lower part it turns into a cylindrical or compressed-cylindrical stem with a diameter of up to 3-4 cm and a length of 1 cm to 1 m or more. The growth of the plate occurs in the zone of its abutment to the stem [6-7].

Using. Due to the iodine content, kelp sugar powder is used in medicine for the treatment and prevention of atherosclerosis and goiter. From finely ground and dried kelp algae, sugary kelp makes excellent filters for capturing heavy metals. When treating industrial wastewater, they act much more efficiently than traditional activated carbon [6-7].

It is possible to obtain bioethanol and biogas. From a ton of algae containing water, 50 liters of ethanol or 20 m³ of biogas are obtained [7].

2. *Laminaria digitata* is a species of brown algae from the genus *Laminaria*, distributed in the North Atlantic from the Kara Sea and Hudson Bay in the north to the Peninsula of Brittany and New York in the south [6, 8].

Biomorphological features. In kelp, the finger-dissected layers are dense, pieces of finger-separated layers are 70-160 cm long and more, 3.5-14 cm wide; the edges of the plates are smooth. The color of the laminaria layers ranges from light olive to dark olive, greenish-brown, red-brown, sometimes black-green. The color is due to the brown pigment fucoxanthin, which masks chlorophyll. The surface of the stratum is covered with a white coating of salts. The smell is peculiar. The taste is salty [6].

Habitat. They form extensive thickets in places with constant water movement, near open shores. On rocks, rocks, it enters the water to a depth of 35 m. Dense and large underwater "algae forests" are formed at a depth of 4-10 m [6].

Using. Kelp is a part of medical preparations that are prescribed for atherosclerosis, in the treatment and prevention of endemic goiter. Also, the extract of kelp finger-dissected has a pronounced concomitant property, being an irritant of gastric secretion, as well as an antidote for upper respiratory tract diseases in persons working with barium salts, radionuclides [6, 8].

3. *Laminaria angustata* is a species of brown algae from the genus kelp, common in the Pacific Ocean from the Sea of Okhotsk to the Sea of Japan [6, 9].

Biomorphological features. The *Laminaria Angustata* layer is narrow – this is a distinctive feature from all algae. It is also worth noting the life expectancy, which is 3-4 years, while other types of Kelp live no more than 2 years [9].

Using. Basically, *Laminaria angustata* is used in preventive and dietary food products and acts as the main component with pronounced medicinal properties, from which polysaccharides, halogens, macro- and microelements are produced by hydrolysis [9-11].

For example, sodium alginate takes an active part in binding and removing radionuclides, heavy metal salts from the body. Alginic acid salts protect the body from the harmful effects of radiation. For these reasons, this type of Kelp is a very good prevention of leukemia and cancer.

Just like other algae, *Laminaria angustata* contains a large amount of iodine in 100 g. it contains 300 mcg. The required amount of iodine for a person's daily allowance is ~ 150 mcg– ~50 g. Due to the high content of iodine, Angustate algae is a good means of preventing thyroid diseases, including endemic goiter [10-11].

This species is unique in its physical properties. During digestion, it gains moisture and increases in volume, irritating the mucous membranes. Due to this, intestinal peristalsis is normalized, such a phenomenon as constipation disappears [11].

Table 1 – Average static chemical composition by useful properties per 1 kg of dry weight

№	Species	Carbohydrates, %	Squirrels, %	Fiber, %	Mineral salts, %	Fats, %	Amounts of iodine, %
1	<i>Saccharina latissima</i>	65	10	9	2,5	3	2,7-3
2	<i>Laminaria digitata</i>	62	9	11	3,2	3	2,5-5
3	<i>Laminaria angustata</i>	60	12	10	3	4	2,9-3,5

In conclusion, it can be concluded that *Laminaria angustata* is the most useful of all the listed species. This species is well distributed, which means that it can adapt to the conditions of industrial production. In addition, according to the average chemical composition and useful properties per 1 kg of dry weight, this species prevails in terms of the composition of the iodine content.

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